

1 **Using peak geometry and shifts in the X-ray spectrum of carbon from electron**
2 **microprobe analysis to determine thermal maturity of organic matter**

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13 **Data Repository**

15 Figure DR 1. Comparison in the C peak position (L-value) (A) and area (B-C) between
16 the same samples and graphite standard before and after instrument maintenance. The C
17 peak areas of the samples from the analysis sessions after maintenance are corrected
18 based on the linear correlation ($y = x \times 0.6098 + 3710.8$) observed in Figure DR. 1B. The
19 error bar of the C peak position (L-value) and area refers to the standard error of the
20 mean. Note that the corrected C peak area are the data used for the parts of Results and
21 Discussion.

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24 Figure DR 2. (A-B) Comparison between the full-width at the half-maximum (FWHM)
25 of the C peak and vitrinite (A) and solid bitumen (B) reflectance. (C) The linear
26 correlation of the area and height of the C peak spectra between samples. VR_o – vitrinite
27 reflectance. BR_o – solid bitumen reflectance. The error bar of the C peak FWHM and
28 height refers to the standard error of the mean.

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30 Figure DR 3. Scatter plot of atomic H/C ratio and C peak area of individual organic
31 matter grains. The data are the same as Figure 3. The error bar in the plot refers to the
32 standard error of the mean.